

Minke's statement Background

The **demand for data and information** is driven by the urgency to act on the current planetary crisis. Global goals, high-level political declarations and landmark agreements (e.g. Agenda 2030, Green Deal, the High Seas Convention, the Plastics Convention and the Kummering-Montreal Global Framework Convention, among others) are accelerating the **requirement for observation and monitoring to understand the current state of the oceans**, identify relationships between parameters and define predictive models.

Data and information shall be supported by high quality, availability and usability to build trust and achievements as quoted in the **IOC-UNESCO Ocean Decade Data &**

Information Strategy (2023)¹ “by 2030: a trusted, inclusive and interconnected ocean data and information system that is actively used for decision-making in support of sustainable management and that also allows for new data, sources, information networks, and solutions to be integrated as the Ocean Decade needs to evolve”.

In the same direction, the EEA progress report for the 8th European Action Plan (2023) identifies areas where the EU is making promising progress. Nevertheless, it highlighted the role of data as crucial in ensuring the transparency and accountability of potential policies enabling evidence-based decisions, serving as the backbone for achieving the ambitious goals of the **Green Deal** efficiently and effectively.

In this scenario, the following issues are of critical importance for the **ocean observation community**:

- **High-quality data and information** to understand the ocean through accurate, accessible and interoperable information.
- **Multi stakeholders’ engagement** to ensure inclusion, diversification, and comprehensive spatial and temporal series.
- **Co-design and partnerships** to monitor, coordinate, and integrate the data and metadata.

The MINKE project

The *Metrology for Integrated Marine Management and Knowledge-Transfer Network*, (**MINKE Project**) is an EU-funded Horizon 2020 initiative aiming to set up a multi-stakeholder network for ocean infrastructure within a new paradigm of quality data. Specifically, it is an H2020 INFRAIA promoting a **starting community** through bringing together 16 key **European marine metrology research infrastructures** to create an innovative quality framework within the **Essential Ocean Variables (EOV)**. The objective is to **build synergies between actors** within the quintuple helix model of innovation, facilitating collaboration and leveraging among the ocean and coastal

¹ <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000385542>

observers community to support the understanding of the blue planet and the sustainable socio-economy system associated with adopting a multidimensional structure of data quality embracing the **accuracy** of the metrological community and the **completeness** of citizen science.

The MINKE project, in its Networking and Engagement with Stakeholders WP4, aims to align the project objectives with the requirements of ongoing initiatives and the needs of end-users in order to consolidate a European network connecting stakeholders from civil society, academia, industry, and decision-makers.

This **dialogue** stems from the key issues identified in the *Stakeholder Engagement Report*² and in the *Report about Progress Project Meeting (PPM) and the Synergy Session (SS) Workshop*. The D4.4. report highlighted that stakeholder engagement plays a key role in implementing the MINKE project because it supports the platform beyond the project life, enabling improvements for future effectiveness steps. The analysis allowed to identify the following approaches throughout the engagement process:

- **Non-interactive stakeholder engagement:** Information sharing and Listening
- **Interactive stakeholder engagement:** Dialogue, Consultation, Collaboration and Joint Decision-making

In addition, during the *Synergy Session* at the *Progress Project Meeting* in Turin (IT) in September 2023, the MINKE project was broken down, assessing its performance using business methodologies such as SWOT and TOWS matrix analysis. **Several key questions** were raised on the following topics: **accuracy and data, dialogue between stakeholders** to facilitate operational integration through harmonisation of procedures and **consolidation of the citizen science into metrology infrastructure**. The questions highlighted in the report have been included in the dialogue to enhance the discussion. With this in mind, one of the objectives was to set up a working group of the marine science and metrology communities to discuss how to approach data and information quality.

² MINKE consortium D4.4 Report on Stakeholder Engagement Metrology for Integrated Marine Management and Knowledge-Transfer Network, MINKE.

The key principles

This statement considers the four principles set out in the Stakeholder Engagement Report (D4.4) as a guide for stakeholder dialogue.

1. Understand: Identify and Analyse

Before aiming to engage a stakeholder, it is crucial to seek to understand their perspective and their potential level of interest and level of engagement with the Research Infrastructure.

2. Be Inclusive

Ensure that the wider network of stakeholders is reached ensuring that broad participation is encouraged and supported by appropriate participation opportunities. No willing stakeholder should be excluded from the process of engagement.

3. Communicate: Early and Often

Choose a method of communication through which they would expect to hear from you, one that will be easy to access and communicate early and often in the process.

4. Build Relationships: Take a long-term view

Utilise the process as an opportunity to build new relationships and strengthen existing ones, thereby increasing their interest in the project's main topics.

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Taking into account the above and considering the opportunity of the **Ocean Decade Conference 2024** in Barcelona brings to the consortium an important scenario in which to promote the debate around the research infrastructures, industries and scientific community allow **the MINKE consortium** to promote a debate concerning

the **stakeholder's commitment** for the improvement of the **global ocean observing system**.

This statement set up the **common, achievable and measurable objectives** in alignment with the Ocean Decade challenges concerning the common priorities and challenges between the different players of the ocean observation community in terms of data.

The **MINKE consortium**,

Take into account the **Barcelona Statement** outcome of the **2024 Ocean Decade Conference**, particularly within the *priorities for ocean knowledge and science generation* and the *cross-cutting issues* listed in terms of engagement of the private sector and *recognition and role of all knowledge systems*.

Stating that MINKE project aims to advance oceanographic research in Europe, promoting the improvement of oceanographic data quality and the consolidation of European networks of sensors and instruments, optimising resources and enhancing the efficiency of data collection and analysis.

Emphasising the importance of integrative activities such as networking, trans-national virtual access and collaborative research, where each sector (civil society, academia, industry and government) has a critical role to play in addressing the complex challenges facing the oceans supporting the quintuple helix model of innovation.

Expressing the goal of MINKE of improving the collective understanding and management of the world's oceans, promoting the transfer of knowledge and the exchange of future perspectives between interested parties, and leaving a lasting legacy in the field of oceanographic research beyond the life of the project.

Establish a group of experts concerning data and information related to data accuracy and completeness that will remain beyond the conference and the project.

Considering the opportunity to propose an Uncertainty Commission to identify potentials and efficiencies for ocean data (standards, best practices and references, constraints, the conceptualisation of data quality efficiency, data workflow, interlaboratory comparisons, training on metrology, etc).

The connection between metrology and the ocean community can shape a working group with complementary capabilities for ocean and coastal observation, supporting the future of oceanographic research and management.

Contributors

- *Vanessa Sarah Salvo, EMBIMOS (EnvironMental and sustainaBility participatory InforMatiOn Systems) Institut de Ciències del Mar -CSIC (ES)*
- *Alina Luna, EMBIMOS (EnvironMental and sustainaBility participatory InforMatiOn Systems) Institut de Ciències del Mar -CSIC (ES)*
- *Giuseppe Magnifico, CNR (ITALY)*
- *Lorenza Evangelista CNR (ITALY)*
- *Alicia Blanco, EuroGOOS · European Global Ocean Observing System (Belgium)*
- *Juan José Dañobeitia, UTM -CSIC (ES)*
- *Pieter Romer, Indigenous Community Liaison Ocean Networks Canada*
- *Peer Fietzek, Kongsberg Discovery (Germany)*
- *Meritxell Turó Silanes, EMBIMOS (EnvironMental and sustainaBility participatory InforMatiOn Systems) Institut de Ciències del Mar -CSIC (ES)*
- *Jaume Piera, EMBIMOS (EnvironMental and sustainaBility participatory InforMatiOn Systems) Institut de Ciències del Mar -CSIC (ES)*

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